

The kinematics of “Don Quixote” and the identity of the “place in La Mancha”: a systemic approach

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Abstract

A multidisciplinary research team using systemic methodologies to analyze the novel *The ingenious hidalgo Don Quixote of La Mancha* has discovered the underlying kinematics in Cervantes’ book: an architecture emerging when the riding times between actual geographic places, expressed in days and nights on horseback, were systemically related to the respective real distances expressed in kilometers. Building on this kinematics, two issues were studied: first, the ground that – according to the novel – Rosinante and Sancho’s donkey could cover in a day’s time; and second, the identity of Cervantes’ mysterious “place in La Mancha”, clearly located in the region known as “Campo de Montiel”, and localised within a reasonable degree of certitude to be one of the three following villages: Villanueva de los Infantes, Alhambra and Carrizosa (in this order) in the Spanish province of Ciudad Real.

Keywords: Quixote; Place in La Mancha; Velocity; Probability.

Introduction

According to Parra-Luna et al. [1], in the four centuries since Cervantes [2] published his novel, no-one has identified the “place in La Mancha” whose name the author cared not to remember, and more recent papers proposing new places likewise lack scientific substantiation. In fact, there is no known attempt to rigorously apply scientific method to determine the exact location of Don Quixote’s “place in La Mancha”.

And yet, today such an approach is perfectly possible thanks to the methodological paradigms proposed in Systems Theory, among others. Indeed, the systemic approach is generally known to provide the best possible selection of variables that not only represent the object studied as a whole, but are themselves inter-related in complex ways. In this case, the analysis involves 24

possible villages, 96 decisive distances and some different assumptions about the speed at which Don Quixote and Sancho Panza were able to ride Rocinante and the donkey, all of which must be taken into account in the systemic whole. All of this precludes simplistic approaches and conclusions obtained on the basis of a single village; rather, the solution should be found by optimizing plausible assumptions and taking account of all the potential candidates.

From the vantage of the first objective, the present study entails “revisiting” research conducted at the Complutense University of Madrid (Parra-Luna et al., 2005) and published under the title *EL QUIJOTE COMO UN SISTEMA DE DISTANCIAS/TIEMPOS: HACIA LA LOCALIZACIÓN DEL LUGAR DE LA MANCHA* (*The novel Don Quixote as a time/distance system: locating the place in*

La Mancha), Ed. Complutense, Madrid. The reply implicit in this article reformulates some of the initial assumptions on which that research was based for the sole purpose of verifying its core hypothesis (location of the “place in La Mancha”), while pursuing a higher degree of accuracy and scientific rigor, whatever the new findings show. The existence of a tacit kinematics in the work is instrumental to test the prior research.

Another recent paper [3] introduces a statistical study of the problem, nevertheless, such statistical approach parts from the dispersion of the data between the different villages. This does not seem reasonable if we consider that the “place in La Mancha” is a village, not the mean of a set of several villages. They defer to a future work the consideration of the uncertainty of the duration of the displacements of Don Quixote and Sancho Panza. In this paper, we part from this uncertainty.

The distance / riding time system

But is the sole existence of a kinematics of any sort in Don Quixote, able to attain the above two objectives? In fact, it is both imaginable and verifiable, thanks to the facts that Cervantes [2] himself provides:

First, the point of departure: Campo de Montiel, a historic/geographic region with a total of 24 villages at the time the novel was written, all at empirically measurable distances from one another. Second, “theoretical” distances (expressed in riding time): between the enigmatic “place in La Mancha” (hereafter referred to as “L”) and three places (Puerto Lápice, Sierra Morena and El Toboso) explicitly cited by Cervantes [2], and one (Munera) implicitly mentioned (Parra-Luna et al, 2005); precisely, we take a

point 2 kilometers SE of Puerto Lápice (end of chapter X) and a point beside Venta de Cárdenas in Sierra Morena from Parra-Luna et al. [1]. All of these are real geographic sites with their respective distances to the region’s 24 villages.

Moreover, these theoretical riding times can be quantified to a reasonable degree of accuracy. These data were structured on the basis of these premises and the information gathered during the research effort described above. Parra-Luna et al. 2005, announced some of the quantitative keys implicit in the novel: among others, the so-called topological solution, which is the one reconsidered here under more certain and verifiable assumptions.

The real distances between villages and the four points of reference

Measuring the distances between villages was an exercise fraught with difficulties due to the inability to objectively establish what would have been the most logical routes and respective distances in the late sixteenth century (differences between maps, new roads, short-cuts, paths and so on). Indeed, the want of a more verifiable system of distances left the researchers with an uncomfortable sensation of uncertainty. Based on the old adage that “La Mancha has no roads, for it is nothing but a road” (plain that it is), this problem was circumvented by taking into account the distances between villages according to the Directorio Cartográfico de España (<http://www.dices.net/mapas>) to reach a consensus on the question with the highest possible degree of objectivity. Table 1 shows these distances.

Origin of coordinates: 38°15'N and 4°53'W	2KmSE Puerto Lapice (123.769,118.096)	Venta Cardenas (120.183,18.236)	El Toboso (164.000,140.189)	Munera (210.163,86.684)
Albaladejo	94.823	64.937	101.366	54.547
Alcubillas	67.32	48.869	85.86	65.815
Alambra	56.635	66.406	68.573	52.66
Almedina	87.727	52.837	99.972	62.438
Cañamares	88.751	75.172	90.172	40.88
Carrizosa	66.026	64.504	75.849	49.981
Castellars	86.738	22.909	111.848	90.058
Cozar	79.819	45.793	96.352	67.24
Fuenllana	75.196	60.524	85.192	52.401
Membrilla	38.424	62.412	68.104	76.85
Montiel	83.94	63.512	91.361	50.721
Ossa	71.16	89.328	64.74	25.627
Puebla P.	93.284	52.148	105.584	65.758
Ruidiera	61.659	81.249	61.864	36.832
S.C. Cañamos	89.97	60.216	98.705	56.355
Solana	45.205	61.849	67.619	67.327
Terriches	93.136	62.214	100.914	56.135
Torre J.A.	86.606	42.07	103.738	72.166
Torres M.	81.266	54.806	93.237	58.633
Torrenueva	74.777	26.705	103.033	89.849
Villahermosa	79.568	66.418	85.86	46.82
Villamanrique	92.326	46.052	107.276	70.869
Villa. Fuente	103.368	67.068	109.437	59.012
Villa. Infantes	73.614	54.841	86.944	58.174

Table 1. Distances in Km from each village of Campo de Montiel to the four points of reference: Puerto Lápice, Venta de Cárdenas , el Toboso and Munera.

Then, we have as premises the conclusions of Parra-Luna et al. [1], in the parent paper, which infers the following times of displacement from L to the four points of reference, with 95% of confidence:

For 2 kms. SE of Puerto Lápice (2SEPL), 22.5 hours \pm 15% (from 19.1 to 25.9 hours).

For El Toboso (ET), 25 hours \pm 10% (from 22.5 to 27.5 hours).

For Venta de Cárdenas (VC), 20 hours \pm 15% (from 17 to 23 hours).

For Munera (M), 20 hours \pm 10% (from 18 to 22 hours).

We also assume:

a) That Cervantes [2] based his estimations on the geographical facts.

b) That the geographical irregularities are distributed homogeneously enough for us to draw the displacement in a straight-line at a constant velocity on a plane, as an approximation.

- c) That travelling velocity is constant and does not depend on either the point of departure or the point of arrival.
- d) That the "Lugar de la Mancha" is an existent locality.

The bounding of the "place in la mancha"

From these premises we can delimit the zone in which \mathbf{L} would have to be. To this end, as $k > 1$, the quotient between its distances to the point of reference which position is given by the vector \mathbf{r}_2 and the point of reference whose position is given by the vector \mathbf{r}_1 , that is to say,

\mathbf{L} will have to be in the circumference of center in $\mathbf{r}_2 + (\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2)k^2 / (k^2 - 1)$ and radius $|\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2|k / (k^2 - 1)$, as can be algebraically verified (Appendix 1 and in <http://www.uv.es/pla/Quixote/append1.htm>). Of course, if $k=1$ then \mathbf{L} will have to be in the perpendicular bisector of \mathbf{r}_1 y \mathbf{r}_2 , given by $(\mathbf{L} - (\mathbf{r}_1 + \mathbf{r}_2)/2) \cdot (\mathbf{r}_1 - \mathbf{r}_2) = 0$.

By assuming a constant velocity, the quotient between the distances will be equal to the quotient between the times of displacement. Thus, taking in twos the four points of reference previously indicated, the quotients between their distances will have to be between the quotient of the ends of the intervals which we have taken for the corresponding times of displacement:

Between 2SEPL and ET, between $k=1.44$ in a way and $k=1.15$ in the another (remember that we always divide the greater by the lesser time so that $k > 1$).

Between 2SEPL and VC, between $k=1.20$ in a way and $k=1.52$ in the another.

Between 2SEPL and M, between $k=1.15$ in a way and $k=1.44$ in the another.

Between ET and VC, between $k=1.02$ in a way and $k=1.62$ in the another.

Between ET and M, between $k=1.02$ and $k=1.53$

Between VC and M, between $k=1.29$ in a way and $k=1.28$ in the another.

Figure 1: Localities in the bounded zone.

We thus obtain two circumferences for each pair of points of reference, which will delimit a zone in which L is located. The intersection of the six zones obtained will define the position of L in accordance with the initial premises. Note that although we would be geometrically able to point to another zone compatible with the times of displacement, this zone would be outside La Mancha, and for displacements to the points of reference, you would require high velocities more typical of a jet than the mounts of Don Quixote and Sancho Panza.

To make these calculations we have taken the geographical coordinates with a precision of one kilometer, provided we can estimate such a distance. As L has to be a locality, we must examine which localities are in the zone delimited. As you can see in the enlarged drawing of the zone in the Figure 1, the only localities which exist in it are **Villanueva de los Infantes**, **Carrizosa** and **Alhambra**. In fact, Alhambra is lightly outside the zone, but its distance to the boundary is smaller than the distance of one kilometer which we had taken as a precision standard for the position of the localities.

Determination of the velocity

For each locality and point of reference we can get an interval of possible velocities by dividing their distance by the ends of the corresponding interval of times of displacement. The intersection of the intervals of possible velocities will give us the set of velocities which were compatible with every time interval of displacement. If this intersection were the empty set, the locality would not be compatible.

We studied the three localities which exist in the bounded zone together with several nearby localities which we use by way of comparison. From the distances in kilometers to the four points of reference we get the intervals of possible velocities in kilometers/hour:

DISTANCE	La Solana	Alhambra	Carrizosa	Villanueva I.	Alcubillas	Fuenllana
to 2SEPL	1.80-2.41	2.20-3.98	2.56-3.48	2.87-3.90	2.61-3.54	2.91-3.95
to ET	2.47-3.02	2.48-3.03	2.76-3.38	3.16-3.87	3.12-3.82	3.09-3.78
to VC	2.69-3.64	2.92-3.95	2.80-3.79	2.41-3.26	2.13-2.88	2.64-3.57
to M	3.05-3.73	2.37-2.90	2.29-2.81	2.64-3.22	3.01-3.68	2.40-2.93

Therefore their intersections, to one decimal figure, are:

Not existing	2.9	2.8	3.2	Not existing	Not existing
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As was predictable, only the three localities which exist in the zone delimited have velocities which are compatible with these displacement time intervals.

Statistical simulation

The algorithm used to simulate a great number (100000) of trips of D. Quixote and Sancho from the “Place in la Mancha” (LM) to the 4 reference points (2Km SE P. Lápice, El Toboso, Munera, Venta de Cárdenas) takes as data the following variables:

- T(4)** : Estimated travelling time in hours from the “Place in la Mancha” (LM) to the 4 reference points (P. Lápice, El Toboso, Munera, Venta de Cárdenas). Considered as a random variable normally distributed with a mean and a standard deviation estimated by experts (see the values stated above in this paper).
- V(21)** : The 21 possible velocities travel of D. Quixote and Sancho (Km/h).
- L(24,2)**: Longitude and latitude of the 24 candidate villages to LM (Km).
- R(4,2)**: Longitude and latitude of the 4 reference points.

From such data, the following variables were calculated:

- D(24,4)**: Real distances from the 24 candidate villages to the 4 reference points (Km).
- C(4,21)**: Calculated distances from LM to the 4 reference points for each of the 21 possible velocities (hours). $C(j,k) = T(j) * V(k)$
- B(24,4,21)**: Estimated distance discrepancies, travelling from LM to the 4 points of reference, between real values and calculated values for each of the 21 possible velocities (hours). $B(i,j,k) = D(i,j) - C(j,k)$
- N(24,21)**: Norm-2 of the distance discrepancies, in relative terms..

$$N(i,k) = \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\frac{B(i,j,k)}{D(i,j)} \right)^2$$

- X**: Index number of the village selected as LM.
- Y**: Index number of the velocity corresponding to X.

$$N(X,Y) = \underset{\substack{i=1,24 \\ j=1,21}}{\text{Min}}(N(i,j))$$

- A(24,21)**: Times that a given selection village-velocity is observed in r simulations with different values of T randomly obtained following a Gaussian distribution.
- AL(24)**: Times that a given village is selected.
- P(24,21,2)**: Confidence intervals (95%) for the probability of each combination village-velocity (Using the Central Limit Theorem).
- PL(24,2)**: Confidence intervals (95%) for the probability of each village.
- PM(24)**: Average probability for each village.
- PC(24,21,2)**: Confidence intervals (95%) for the conditioned probabilities of each velocity in each village. $PC(i,j,1)=P(i,j,1)/PL(i,2)$; $PC(i,j,2)=P(i,j,2)/PL(i,1)$
- VI(24,2)**: Confidence intervals (95%) for the average velocity from each village.

$$VI(i,k) = \sum_{j=1}^{21} V(j) \cdot PC(i,j,k)$$

- VM(2)**: Confidence interval (95%) for the average velocity of the travellers considering all possible velocities.

$$VM(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{24} VI(i,k) \cdot PM(i)$$

The detailed algorithm can be found in Appendix 2 and in

<http://www.uv.es/~Caselles/Quixote/append2.htm>

Conclusions

In accordance with the premises from which we have started and with the margin of error considered:

- a) The "Place in La Mancha" had to be Villanueva de los Infantes, Alhambra or Carrizosa.
- b) With a 95% reliability.

- the probability of Villanueva de los Infantes is between 0.353 and 0.358, with a velocity between 2.975 and 3.114 kms/h.
- the probability of Alhambra is between 0.312 and 0.317, with a velocity between 2.687 and 2.82 kms/h.
- the probability of Carrizosa is between 0.18 and 0.184, with a velocity between 2.674 and 2.812 kms/h.
- Nearby villages with their respective probability and velocity intervals are: Alcubillas (0.089-0.092)(2.902-3.138), Fuenllana (0.043-0.044)(2.884,3.093).

- c) With a 95% reliability, the global mean velocity had to be between 2.789 and 2.935 kms/h.

These results are consistent with those of Parra-Luna et al. [1].

References

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Appendix 1

Determination of a point by the ratio of the distances to two points in a plane.

If $k=|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_2|/|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_1|>1$, then \mathbf{L} will be in the circumference with centre in $\mathbf{C}=\mathbf{r}_2+(\mathbf{r}_1-\mathbf{r}_2)k^2/(k^2-1)$ and radius $R=|\mathbf{r}_1-\mathbf{r}_2|k/(k^2-1)$.

To verify it, we will develop the expressions $|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_2|/|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_1|=1$, with $k>1$, and the equation of the circumference $|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{C}|=R$ to arrive to the same system of equations.

From $|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{C}|=R$,

$$|\mathbf{L} - \mathbf{r}_2 - (\mathbf{r}_1-\mathbf{r}_2)k^2/(k^2-1)| = |\mathbf{r}_1-\mathbf{r}_2|k/(k^2-1)$$

$$|(k^2-1)\mathbf{L} - (k^2-1)\mathbf{r}_2 - k^2(\mathbf{r}_1-\mathbf{r}_2)| = k|\mathbf{r}_1-\mathbf{r}_2|$$

$$|(k^2-1)\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{r}_2 - k^2\mathbf{r}_1| = k|\mathbf{r}_1-\mathbf{r}_2|$$

$$|(k^2-1)\mathbf{L} + \mathbf{r}_2 - k^2\mathbf{r}_1|^2 = k^2|\mathbf{r}_1-\mathbf{r}_2|^2$$

$$(k^2-1)^2|\mathbf{L}|^2 + |\mathbf{r}_2|^2 + k^4|\mathbf{r}_1|^2 + 2(k^2-1)\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_2 - 2k^2(k^2-1)\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_1 - 2k^2\mathbf{r}_1\cdot\mathbf{r}_2 = k^2(|\mathbf{r}_1|^2+|\mathbf{r}_2|^2-2\mathbf{r}_1\cdot\mathbf{r}_2)$$

$$(k^2-1)^2|\mathbf{L}|^2 + |\mathbf{r}_2|^2 + k^4|\mathbf{r}_1|^2 + 2(k^2-1)\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_2 - 2k^2(k^2-1)\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_1 = k^2|\mathbf{r}_1|^2 + k^2|\mathbf{r}_2|^2$$

$$(k^2-1)^2|\mathbf{L}|^2 - (k^2-1)|\mathbf{r}_2|^2 + k^2(k^2-1)|\mathbf{r}_1|^2 + 2(k^2-1)\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_2 - 2k^2(k^2-1)\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_1 = 0$$

$$(k^2-1)|\mathbf{L}|^2 - |\mathbf{r}_2|^2 + k^2|\mathbf{r}_1|^2 + 2\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_2 - 2k^2\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_1 = 0 \quad [1]$$

From $|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_2|/|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_1|=k$,

$$|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_2| = k|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_1|$$

$$|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_2|^2 = k^2|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_1|^2$$

$$|\mathbf{L}|^2 + |\mathbf{r}_2|^2 - 2\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_2 = k^2(|\mathbf{L}|^2 + |\mathbf{r}_1|^2 - 2\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_1)$$

$$0 = (k^2-1)|\mathbf{L}|^2 - |\mathbf{r}_2|^2 + k^2|\mathbf{r}_1|^2 + 2\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_2 - 2k^2\mathbf{L}\cdot\mathbf{r}_1 \quad [\text{equal to 1, q.e.d.}]$$

If $k=|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_2|/|\mathbf{L}-\mathbf{r}_1|=1$, then \mathbf{L} will be in the perpendicular bisector of the segment between \mathbf{r}_1 and \mathbf{r}_2 , that is to say, the straight line perpendicular to $\mathbf{r}_1-\mathbf{r}_2$ which crosses through its middle point $(\mathbf{r}_1+\mathbf{r}_2)/2$. The equation of this perpendicular bisector is

$$(\mathbf{L}-(\mathbf{r}_1+\mathbf{r}_2)/2)\cdot(\mathbf{r}_1-\mathbf{r}_2)=0.$$

Appendix 2

The algorithm used to simulate a great number (100000) of trips of D. Quixote and Sancho

Data:

T(4) : Estimated travelling time from the LM (LM) to the 4 referencie points (P. Lápice, El Toboso, Munera, Venta de Cárdenas)(hours). Considered as a random variable normally distributed with a mean and a standard deviation estimated by experts.

V(21) : Possible velocities for travels of D. Quixote and Sancho (Km/h).

L(24,2): Longitude and latitude of the 24 candidate villages to be LM (Km) from the point (336,4234).

R(4,2): Longitude and latitude of the 4 reference points.

Calculated variables:

D(24,4): Real distances from the 24 candidate villages to the 4 reference points (Km).

$$D(i, j) = \sqrt{(L(i,1) - R(j,1))^2 + (L(i,2) - R(j,2))^2}$$

C(4,21): Calculated distances from LM to the 4 reference points for each of the 21 possible velocities (hours).

$$C(j,k) = T(j) * V(k)$$

B(24,4,21): Estimated distance discrepancies, travelling from LM to the 4 points of reference, between real values and calculated values for each of the 21 possible velocities (hours).

$$B(i,j,k) = D(i,j) - C(j,k)$$

N(24,21): Norm-2 of the distance discrepancies, in relative value.

$$N(i, k) = \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\frac{B(i, j, k)}{D(i, j)} \right)^2$$

X: Index number of the village selected as LM.

Y: Index number of the velocity corresponding to X.

$$N(X, Y) = \text{Min}_{\substack{i=1,24 \\ j=1,21}} (N(i, j))$$

A(24,21): Times that a given selection village-velocity is observed in r simulations with different values of T randomly obtained following a Gaussian distribution.

For i from 1 to 24 and

For j from 1 to 21, do:

If (X=i and Y=j) then A(i,j) increases one unit

Next j

Next i

AL(24): Times that a given village is selected.

For i from 1 to 24 and

For j from 1 to 21, do:

Increase AL(i) with A(i,j)

Next j

Next i

P(24,21,2): Confidence intervals (95%) for the probability of each combination village-velocity (Central Limit Theorem). Being nr the number of repetitions of the simulation process.

Let $pmin=1$ and $pmax=0$
 For i from 1 to 24 and
 For j from 1 to 21 and
 For p from 0'001 to 1 step 0'001 do:

$$h = \frac{A(i, j) - nr \cdot p}{\sqrt{nr \cdot p \cdot (1 - p)}}$$

 If h is between -1'96 and +1'96 then
 If p is smaller than $pmin$ then let $pmin=p$
 If p is greater than $pmax$ then let $pmax=p$
 End If
 Next p
 $P(i, j, 1)=pmin$; $P(i, j, 2)=pmax$
 Next j
 Next i

PL(24,2): Confidence intervals (95%) for the probability of each village.
 Here there is a similar algorithm to the one used for **P** but substituting $A(i, j)$ by $AL(i)$ and $P(i, j, 1)$ and $P(i, j, 2)$ by $PL(i, 1)$ and $PL(i, 2)$.

PM(24): Average probability for each village.
 $PM(i)=(PL(i, 1)+PL(i, 2))/2$

PC(24,21,2): Confidence intervals (95%) for the conditioned probabilities of each velocity in each village.

$$PC(i, j, 1)=P(i, j, 1)/PL(i, 2)$$

$$PC(i, j, 2)=P(i, j, 2)/PL(i, 1)$$

VI(24,2): Confidence intervals (95%) for the average velocity from each village.

$$VI(i, k) = \sum_{j=1}^{21} V(j) \cdot PC(i, j, k)$$

VM(2): Confidence interval (95%) for the average velocity of the travelers considering all possible velocities.

$$VM(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{24} VI(i, k) \cdot PM(i)$$